

Cell-DRL Reconstructs Unseen Cellular Paths in Health and Disease

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Abstract

Diseases can be conceived as deviations from healthy cell state manifolds. Numerous methods leverage the power of single-cell RNA sequencing for reconstructing cell state trajectories. Such approaches generally rely on sufficient sampling of cell states covering the entire trajectory. Since patients typically undergo treatment only after symptoms have already manifested, clinical samples covering intermediate disease states are generally unavailable, limiting our ability to understand the underlying intermediate paths of disease evolution. Reconstruction of missing states on disease trajectories is a major open challenge. To overcome the limitations of current approaches, we developed Cell-DRL, a deep reinforcement learning agent capable of geometric reasoning on biological manifolds, generating actions in gene expression space, and learning stochastic policies to reconstruct trajectories connecting two distant anchoring cellular states. We validated Cell-DRL on ground truths scenarios by hiding intermediate states and demonstrated the capacity to reconstruct multipotent hematopoietic stem cell states from distinct lineage-specific progenitors. We showcased the power of Cell-DRL to recover unseen cellular states in healthy as well as disease scenarios at the individual patient level. Finally, Cell-DRL predicted a novel human cardiac fibroblast-to-cardiomyocyte trans-differentiation path, which we validated in vitro. We expect that Cell-DRL will be crucial to gain valuable mechanistic insights into the development and progression of diseases at high temporal resolution.

Introduction

The development of single-cell genomics techniques over the last decade has made it possible to decipher the cell state composition of biological systems across molecular layers¹. Most prominently, single-cell mRNA-sequencing (scRNA-seq) has revolutionized our ability to resolve cell state manifolds and to reconstruct cellular differentiation trajectories from snapshot data of biological systems with constant turnover, or from developmental time-course data. A multitude of computational approaches have been established to infer differentiation trajectories from such data². In general, these methods rely on sufficient coverage of the entire trajectory by single-cell transcriptomes sampled from all intermediate states and are incapable of reconstructing

49 unseen cellular states^{3,4}. When studying dynamical cell state transitions using *in vitro*
50 systems such as organoids, or animal models, an appropriate experimental design can
51 ensure the representation of the full spectrum of intermediate states. Nonetheless,
52 technical biases, e.g., due to the difficulty of isolating particular cell states from a tissue,
53 or due to unknown developmental dynamics represent considerable challenges.
54 Insufficient sampling of cell states poses a fundamental problem for the reconstruction
55 of disease trajectories from human clinical samples.

56 According to the disease state trajectory (DST) model (Figure 1A), diseases may evolve
57 continuously over time^{3,5}. Many common diseases, such as cancer, are characterized by
58 a sequential emergence of aberrant cell states within a tissue. The developmental
59 trajectories of such diseases may initiate from potentially predisposed healthy cell states
60 and undergo a sequence of intermediate states by accumulating genetic and epigenetic
61 aberrations to result in a full-blown disease state, frequently giving rise to clones with
62 independent trajectories and mutational patterns⁶. Knowledge of disease trajectories
63 would arguably lead to a deeper understanding of the mechanistic underpinnings of
64 disease progression and facilitate the development of diagnostics and therapeutic
65 interventions for early interception of diseases. However, clinical samples of
66 intermediate disease states are usually not available (Figure 1A), since patients visit the
67 clinic only after the manifestation of symptoms.

68 Inspired by the way humans learn, we designed a deep reinforcement learning
69 framework (Cell-DRL) for the inference of unseen cell states to reconstruct differentiation
70 trajectories from datasets lacking samples of intermediate states. Cell-DRL utilizes deep
71 neural networks for training an agent to interact with an environment in a series of
72 discrete time steps. At each timestep, the agent observes the current state of the
73 environment and takes an action. This action leads to a new state of the environment
74 and the agent receives a reward signal indicating the desirability of the outcome. The
75 goal of the agent is to learn a policy, i.e., a mapping from states to actions, that
76 maximizes the cumulative reward⁷. In our Cell-DRL framework, we designed an agent
77 that learns a policy to reconstruct intermediate cell states within the permissible cell state
78 manifold connecting two separated anchoring cell states on a common trajectory
79 measured by scRNA-seq. The Cell-DRL agent can explore the gene expression space at
80 single-cell resolution.

81 We challenged Cell-DRL with multiple biological scenarios in health and diseases. We
82 show that the Cell-DRL agent can reconstruct the cell cycle and human lung cancer
83 epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) states over time when hiding intermediate
84 states. The reconstruction capacity of Cell-DRL even extends to multipotent cell states as
85 demonstrated by reconstructing masked mouse hematopoietic stem cell states from
86 disconnected hematopoietic progenitor states of erythrocytes and granulocytes. Focusing
87 on disease scenarios, we show that Cell-DRL can reconstruct two key intermediate
88 disease states of multiple myeloma (MM) evolution for an *in vivo* mouse model and has
89 the capacity to predict disease trajectories and unseen cellular states of individual MM
90 patients. Finally, we applied Cell-DRL to infer a novel trans-differentiation path from
91 human cardiac fibroblast (HCF) to cardiomyocytes (CM) which we validated
92 experimentally.

93 Cell-DRL represents a novel AI agent capable of geometric reasoning on biological
94 manifolds, addressing a crucial gap in single-cell genomics by reconstructing
95 intermediate cellular states and tracing unseen disease paths. Unlike current advances

96 in neural language-based reasoning models like OpenAI o1⁸, DeepSeek-R1⁹, and others,
97 which excel in relational reasoning, Cell-DRL proposes novel geometric reasoning
98 principles to the single-cell genomics field. We developed the Cell-DRL environment as
99 an innovative new paradigm for modeling cell state transitions and as a basis for future
100 method development to gain mechanistic insights into disease evolution and cellular
101 differentiation paths in general.

102

103 **Results**

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105 **Cell-DRL agent and environment architecture**

106 We developed Cell-DRL, a novel deep reinforcement learning architecture (Figure 1B,
107 C and Extended Data Fig. 1A) to reconstruct missing transcriptomic states on cellular
108 differentiation trajectories connecting two anchoring states profiled by scRNA-seq
109 (Methods).

110 Briefly, the Cell-DRL environment is composed of an agent that can observe cellular
111 states, take actions to generate new cellular states, and observe the consequences of
112 taking such actions. The environment emits a reward signal given the cellular state
113 distance between the generated and target states. If the generated state is closer to the
114 target state, the Cell-DRL agent receives a positive reward to reinforce taking such actions
115 consequently in future steps. Otherwise, if the generated state is far away from the target
116 state, the agent receives a negative reward to decrease the probability of taking such
117 actions in future steps. In this way, the agent experiences the environment over hundreds
118 of thousands of steps, in order to learn how to generate the right sequence of actions for
119 reconstructing intermediate cell state trajectories consistent with the permissible cell
120 state manifold (Extended Data Fig. 1B).

121 The input to Cell-DRL is a merged single-cell gene expression matrix of the two
122 anchoring cellular states (*S₁*, *S₂*). The merged matrix is pushed to the data processing
123 unit and prepared for the Cell-DRL environment (Methods, Extended Data Fig. 1A). To
124 design reasoning agents on a cell state manifold, we incorporated several components
125 into the Cell-DRL architecture:

126 (1) The Cell-DRL environment is designed as a Markov decision process (MDP)
127 (Methods, Extended Data Fig. 1C), where we implicitly assume that a cell's fate only
128 depends on the current cellular state, regardless of the entire cell state history.

129 (2) The Cell-DRL observation space is defined as the manifold of all possible cell states
130 that can be visited by the agent (Figure 1C).

131 (3) The reconstruction field (RF) is constrained by distances to the anchoring cell states
132 in the observation space. It guides the reconstruction of the relevant region within the
133 cell state manifold by the agent (Methods, Figure 1D, E).

134 (4) The Actions Generator and Controller (AGC) unit enables the agent to reconstruct
135 cell states and to navigate in observation space (Figure 1C). The AGC unit is composed
136 of two subunits, termed Gen-Unit and Do-Unit (Methods, Figure 1F). To harness the
137 power of linear models for interpretable cell state reconstruction, the AGC unit calculates
138 a covariance matrix of the merged expression matrix of the two anchoring cell states.
139 This covariance matrix is decomposed into principal components (PC) by singular value
140 decomposition (SVD). These PCs capture the gene-gene covariance structure and are
141 utilized to guide the generation process within the Gen-Unit. The Gen-Unit generates
142 new cellular states by sampling from a multivariate Gaussian distribution, modeling

143 changes of the individual PCs, where three control parameters (μ_{gen}, σ_{gen} and ζ) are
144 governed by the Do-Unit. These actions generate novel cellular states in gene expression
145 space which respect the gene-gene covariance structure inherent in the anchoring cell
146 states, aiming to confine the observation space to the actual cell state manifold. Hence,
147 the Do-unit enables the agent to control the Gen-Unit during the learning process.

148 (5) The reward function was designed to be dependent on the cellular state loss (CSL),
149 which quantifies the similarity of the generated cellular state to the target cellular state
150 based on Kullback-Leibler divergence, cosine similarity, and entropy regularization
151 terms, and to satisfy the learning bound score (LBS) objective function (Methods, Figure
152 1D and E). The reward function reinforces the agent to reconstruct cellular events in the
153 reconstruction field of interest.

154 (6) The Cell-DRL policy π_{θ} is parametrized by a neural network which is optimized via
155 gradient ascent to maximize the reward objective (Methods and Extended Data Fig. 1D).
156 In addition to the standard reward objective, we optimize a maximum entropy
157 objective^{10,11} to enable the agent to alternate between exploration and exploitation
158 phases during reconstruction. Cell-DRL generates stochastic policies by learning a
159 probability distribution over actions given the collected observations generated by the
160 AGC unit.

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162 To demonstrate the capacity of Cell-DRL for reconstructing unseen intermediate cell
163 states, we challenged the method with different scenarios of varying complexity. In each
164 case, we start with a known continuous cell state trajectory profiled by scRNA-seq as
165 ground truths but feed only an initial and a target anchoring cell state into the method to
166 reconstruct the unseen intermediate states. This strategy facilitates the evaluation of the
167 capacity to reconstruct hidden states by directly comparing them to the unseen ground
168 truths states (Extended Data Fig. 1E). The challenges for Cell-DRL span the reconstruction
169 of simple linear trajectories, the reconstruction of multipotent states, and more complex
170 disease scenarios. We devised analytical approaches to quantify the robustness of
171 intermediate state reconstruction at the level of cell embeddings and across genes.

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Figure 1: Cell-DRL Agent and Environment Architecture.

- A. Schematic representation of the disease state trajectory model explaining the emergence of disease state trajectories over our lifetime.
- B. Overview of the Cell-DRL environment architecture where blue dots (1) represent the initial cellular state, orange dots (2) represent the generated cellular states after the agent has taken actions, and red dots (3) represent the target cellular states.
- C. Schematic representation of the observation space of healthy and disease cellular states (right), where each dot represents a real data point collected from experimental and clinical data. By zooming into the data of the two states in the small box, we focus on the reconstruction field of interest given the initial and target states of interest. The agent, through trial and error, tries to

186 generate cellular states and trajectories in the reconstruction area, approximating the true cellular
187 state manifold.

188 **D, E.** Schematic representation of the learning bound scores. By providing initial and target states, we
189 can define the reconstruction area of interest. We also define the positive reward area, where we
190 encourage the agent to take actions and generate cellular states within that area. Conversely, the
191 negative reward area is defined to discourage the agent from generating cellular states in that
192 region.

193 **F.** The action generator and controller unit, where we decompose the covariance matrix of the initial
194 and target cellular states using the SVD algorithm. We then feed the singular value and vector
195 matrices into the Gen-Unit to generate novel cellular states. The generator unit is controlled by
196 the Do-Unit, which the agent uses to manage the generation parameters of the Gen-Unit.

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198 **Reconstructing the S phase of the cell cycle**

199 The cell cycle is a highly regulated biological process of cell proliferation, composed of
200 four subsequent stages, Gap1 (G1), synthesis (S), Gap2 (G2), and mitosis (M). During the
201 S phase, the DNA of a cell is replicated, followed by cell division during the M phase.
202 G1 and G2 phases are intermittent growth periods and prepare for DNA replication and
203 mitosis, respectively. The sequence of the G1, S, and G2 phases is referred to as
204 interphase. The cell cycle is tightly controlled by a complex network of regulatory
205 elements¹². To test the capacity of Cell-DRL for reconstructing intermediate states, we
206 focused on murine hematopoietic progenitor cells going through interphase profiled by
207 scRNA-seq¹³ (Figure 2A). We challenged the agent by presenting data for G1 and G2/M
208 as anchoring cell states to reconstruct the S phase (Figure 2B). During the training phase,
209 the agent went through an exploration phase followed by an exploitation phase and
210 ultimately generated cellular states in the reconstruction field (RF) of interest (H=3 steps,
211 Extended Data Fig. 2A-C). After training, the agent was able to generate cell states
212 covering the intermediate S phase, as well as the anchoring G1 and G2/M phases as
213 assessed by the overlap with ground truths S phase scRNA-seq data in the embedded
214 space that were hidden during training (Figure 2C and E and Extended Data Fig. 2D and
215 E). This observation is supported by a high and specific transcriptome correlation
216 between ground truths and generated data across all cell cycle stages (Figure 2D,
217 Extended Data Fig. 2F and G). These results demonstrate the capacity of Cell-DRL to
218 reconstruct unseen states on a linear trajectory.

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220 **Reconstructing the epithelial-mesenchymal transition in human lung** 221 **cancer**

222 Having demonstrated the successful reconstruction of the cell cycle, we sought to
223 explore whether the Cell-DRL agent could reconstruct an entire biological process
224 involving shifts in cell identities.

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231 **Figure 2: Reconstruction of Linear Cellular State Trajectories for the Cell Cycle and**
232 **Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition.**

- 233 A. Uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction (UMAP) representation
234 of the cell cycle cellular states: G1 (green dots), S phase (yellow dots), and G2/M phase (red dots).
235 B. UMAP representation of the two-state challenge, indicating the G1 and G2/M phases provided to
236 the Cell-DRL agent as initial and target state, respectively.
237 C. UMAP representation of the co-embedding for cell cycle real and generated cellular states.
238 D. Heatmap depicting correlation patterns between real and generated data in each Leiden cluster.
239 E. Density plot of UMAP representation illustrating co-localization patterns of cellular states within
240 each cell cycle phase and the generated states overlaying the cellular state manifold.
241 F. UMAP representation of the epithelial-mesenchymal transition process single-cell RNA-seq data
242 across experimental time points.
243 G. UMAP representation for the two-state challenge, presenting the Cell-DRL agent data from Day 0
244 and Day 3 cellular states.
245 H. Density plot of UMAP representation showing co-localization patterns of cellular states from Day
246 0, Day 3, and generated states overlaying the cellular state manifold.
247 I. UMAP representation displaying co-embedding of real and generated data. Colors indicate real
248 and generated data within each Leiden cluster.
249 J. UMAP representation displaying EMT gene signature scores during the transition process.
250 K. Violinplot depicting EMT scores of real and generated cellular states across the Leiden clusters.

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252 We chose to investigate the epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), which involves a
253 transformation of a cell identity from an epithelial to a mesenchymal state. EMT is a
254 complex process regulated by several key signaling pathways, including the Wnt and
255 transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β) pathways, which are crucial for cancer
256 progression in metastatic conditions¹⁴.

257 To study the temporal dynamics of the EMT process, we analyzed scRNA-seq data from
258 a lung cancer cell line (A549) treated with the EMT-inducing factor TGFB1 over seven
259 days¹⁵ (Figure 2F). We challenged Cell-DRL by introducing the scRNA-seq data of day
260 0 and day 3 as anchoring states to reconstruct the intermediate transition states (Figure
261 2G). After training, the agent was able to reconstruct the entire manifold (H=10 steps)
262 including data at 8 hours and 1 day (Figure 2H, Extended Data Fig. 3A-E). The specificity
263 of the reconstructed state was supported by the integration with the hidden ground truths
264 intermediate states in the embedded space and co-clustering of real and generated data
265 (Figure 2I). The co-embedding reflects a gradual increase of an EMT signature (Methods)
266 with time (Figure 2J), consistently observed in real and generated cells across clusters
267 (Figure 2K). We also measured consistent expression of individual EMT marker genes
268 such as *TGFB1*, *MYC*, *SOX4*, and *ELF3* in real and generated cells within specific clusters
269 (Extended Data Fig. 3F).
270 These findings indicate that the agent was able to reconstruct the entire EMT process
271 accurately and highlight the potential of Cell-DRL to reconstruct complex biological
272 processes involving shifts in cell identity in the context of disease dynamics.

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274 **Cell-DRL reconstructs non-linear differentiation paths in hematopoiesis** 275 **and development**

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277 To test the ability of Cell-DRL to accurately reconstruct complex intermediate states on
278 non-linear trajectories, we applied the method to the hematopoietic system.
279 Hematopoiesis takes place in the adult bone marrow and involves the gradual
280 differentiation of hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) into various types of blood cells,
281 including erythrocytes, platelets, and different types of immune cells such as
282 lymphocytes, neutrophils, and monocytes. This process is characterized by a continuous
283 hierarchy of transcriptional cell states, as HSCs progress through differentiation into
284 multipotent progenitors (MPPs) and eventually commit to a single lineage^{16,17}. To go
285 beyond the challenge of reconstructing linear differentiation trajectories, we tested the
286 capacity of Cell-DRL to reconstruct the HSC and MPP states from anchoring cell states
287 of lineage-committed progenitors.

288 For this task, we utilized scRNA-seq data from murine Kit⁺ hematopoietic progenitors¹⁸
289 comprising populations of HSCs, MPPs, and lineage-specific progenitors annotated
290 based on marker gene expression (Figure 3A and Extended Data Fig. 4A). We then
291 presented two progenitor states, namely the erythroid and neutrophil progenitors, as
292 anchoring states to the agent and tasked it with reconstructing the HSC and MPP
293 populations (Figure 3B). Since these hidden states are known to express specific gene
294 signatures associated with multipotency and are expected to comprise progenitors
295 exhibiting transcriptional fate bias towards other lineages this task represents a significant
296 challenge. The co-embedding of the generated and the ground truths data, including the
297 representation of the real HSC and MPP states, suggested a faithful reconstruction of the
298 entire early hematopoietic hierarchy, in particular, the stem and progenitor states (Figure
299 3C and Extended Data Fig. 4B-F).

300 We assessed the accuracy of the generated intermediate stem and progenitor states by
301 performing Leiden clustering (Extended Data Fig. 4D) and focused on the subset of
302 intermediate clusters (0,1,2,3, and 5) to analyze the gene expression correlation between
303 real and generated data. We observed a high and specific correlation of gene expression

304 between real and generated cells within each cluster (Figure 3D). Moreover, the agent
305 was able to accurately recover differentially expressed genes of each cluster (n=150) as
306 well as highly variable genes (n=3000), reflected by Pearson's correlation coefficients of
307 up to 0.96 and 0.85, respectively (Figure 3E). In particular, the generated data
308 recapitulated specific expression patterns of HSC markers (*Cd34*, *Cd48*, *Hlf*, *Procr* and
309 *Slamf1*), Megakaryocyte progenitor markers (*Mpl*), erythroid lineage transcription factors
310 (*Gata1* and *Gata2*) and other progenitor marker genes¹⁹ (Figure 3F, Extended Data Fig.
311 4H and I). We note that we obtained similar results with separate embeddings for real
312 and generated data (Extended Data Fig. 4J and K) and that consistent correlation analysis
313 using Spearman's coefficient (Extended Data Fig. 5A) suggests that highly expressed
314 genes do not have a dominant influence.

315 We performed differentiation-pseudotime inference by running diffusion pseudotime on
316 the real and generated data (Methods) to examine pseudotime expression profiles of
317 specific marker genes associated with lineage identities (Figure 3G, H and Extended Data
318 Fig. 5G). For simplicity, we anchored the trajectory in the neutrophil progenitor state and
319 followed a linear trajectory traversing the HSC compartment toward the erythrocyte
320 branch. As we move away from the neutrophil progenitors towards the MPP
321 compartment, we observed gradual downregulation of neutrophil markers (*Elane*, *Gfi1*,
322 and *Mpo*), followed by a transient upregulation of MPP markers (*Cd48*, *Sox4*, *Cd27* and
323 *Cd34*), and ultimately, upon entering the erythrocyte branch, gradual upregulation of
324 erythroid lineage markers (*Gata1*, *Car1*, *Car2* and *Gfi1b*), consistent with known
325 differentiation dynamics. These results show that Cell-DRL could accurately identify the
326 correct sequence of transcriptional events governing neutrophil and erythrocyte
327 differentiation from hematopoietic stem cells.

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Figure 3: Reconstruction of non-linear cell state trajectories in hematopoiesis and development.

- A. UMAP representation of murine hematopoietic stem and progenitor single-cell RNA-seq data with cell type labels based on marker gene expression. Colors indicate Leiden clusters.
- B. UMAP representation for the two-state challenge, presenting neutrophil progenitors and erythroid progenitors to the Cell-DRL agent.
- C. UMAP representation displaying co-embedding of real and generated data with the Leiden clusters.

- 338 D. Heatmap illustrating correlation patterns between real and generated data within each Leiden
339 cluster.
- 340 E. Barplot indicating Pearson's correlation coefficients between the top 150 differentially expressed
341 (DE) genes for real and generated data, and between highly variable genes (HVGs) within Leiden
342 clusters.
- 343 F. UMAP representation of intermediate cellular states with a color code highlighting estimated
344 pseudotime values.
- 345 G. Heatmap displaying gene expression of key marker genes and transcription factors regulating HSCs
346 and MMPs states across latent pseudotime of the Cell-DRL generated cellular states.
- 347 H. UMAP representation of mouse embryonic developmental atlas sampled from embryonic days E6.5
348 to E8.5.
- 349 I. Density plot of the UMAP representation of the integrated real and generated data showing the
350 reconstructed sequence of cellular states from the primitive streak to the three embryonic germ
351 layers: ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm.
- 352 J. Heatmap illustrating correlation patterns of gene expression between real and generated
353 intermediate states within intermediate Leiden clusters of the three germ layers.

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355 The generative capabilities of Cell-DRL allow for the generation of multiple realizations
356 of connecting intermediate paths. To identify the optimal trajectories linking the initial
357 and target cellular states (Extended Data Fig. 5B and C), we developed optimal
358 intermediate paths inference (Methods) generating multiple plausible paths that could be
359 taken during a biological process.

360 We utilized the reconstruction of hematopoietic stem and progenitor cells to assess the
361 dependence of Cell-DRL on the input data more systematically. First, we increased the
362 distance of the anchoring states by providing the most mature erythroid and neutrophil
363 cell states (clusters 5 and 7) as anchoring states (Extended Data Fig. 5D). Despite the low
364 number of cells in these clusters (476 cells), the reconstruction accuracy remained high
365 (Extended Data Fig. 5E and F). By systematically varying the size of the anchoring cell
366 states, we demonstrate that the reconstruction accuracy starts to drop for clusters below
367 900 cells for both anchoring cellular states (Extended Data Fig. 5G). The run time of Cell-
368 DRL only marginally depends on the size of the anchoring states, since only the SVD
369 computation is significantly affected by the dataset size (Extended Data Fig5 H).

370 We further tested if Cell-DRL would hallucinate the expression of a gene completely
371 switched off in the anchoring states, by setting the expression of *Cd34* to zero in all cells
372 (Extended Data Fig. 5I). In this scenario, the agent did not recover the transient expression
373 of *Cd34* in the generated progenitor cells. Hence, reliable reconstruction of gene
374 expression relies on the gene-gene covariance information encoded within the
375 anchoring states, even if these genes are only sparsely expressed (Extended Data Fig. 5D,
376 F, J, and K). Additionally, we demonstrated that the Cell-DRL agent can reconstruct non-
377 linear expression dynamics and model bifurcation events by defining an initial root state
378 and two distinct terminal states (Extended Data Fig. 6A-E).

379 To further validate the reconstructed intermediate paths, we introduced a "Plausibility
380 Score" based on the Bures-Wasserstein distance²⁰ (Methods). This score measures how
381 closely a generated path aligns with an observed reference single-cell atlas (Extended
382 Data Fig. 6F and G). A higher Plausibility Score indicates greater similarity between the
383 generated path and the reference atlas, suggesting a higher likelihood that the path
384 reflects an actual biological process. This quantitative measure allows a comparative
385 evaluation of the biological relevance of multiple reconstructed paths.

386 Furthermore, we showed that independent Cell-DRL agents exhibited an advanced
387 capability to reconstruct complex biological processes and non-linear trajectories (Figure

388 3H and I), including the formation of the three embryonic germ layers (ectoderm,
389 mesoderm, endoderm) and the primitive streak during mouse embryogenesis from E6.5
390 to E8.5 (Extended Data Fig. 7)²¹. We note that the reconstructed intermediate states
391 exhibit high and specific transcriptome similarity with the ground truth intermediate state
392 data of the respective germ layer (Figure 3J). The ability to reconstruct such complex
393 non-linear dynamics is crucial for understanding how complex structures and tissues
394 arise from a relatively homogeneous group of cells in the early embryo and during
395 developmental processes.

396 Finally, we aimed to compare Cell-DRL with alternative approaches for generating
397 unseen cell states. Although methods relying on RNA velocity²² or optimal transport²³
398 are in principle capable of extrapolating or interpolating cell states on short timescales,
399 they were not designed to reconstruct cellular transcriptomes. Another strategy, scGen²⁴
400 proposed linear vector arithmetic in the latent space of a variational autoencoder (VAE)
401 to transfer perturbation responses from one cell type to another. This motivates the idea
402 that linear interpolation in the latent space of a VAE could enable reconstructing unseen
403 cell states. We considered extending the scGen modeling strategy towards this
404 application (Methods) and tested this approach on the challenging scenario of
405 reconstructing unseen hematopoietic stem and multipotent progenitor cells from
406 erythrocyte and neutrophil progenitors. In contrast to Cell-DRL, this approach generated
407 a large cloud of data (Extended Data Fig. 8A), highly dissimilar to the ground truths data
408 with gene reconstruction errors, exemplified by expression of the neutrophil marker
409 *Ela1* and the erythroid marker *Car1*, and downregulation of *Gata2* in the generated
410 intermediate states (Extended Data Fig. 8B).

411

412 **Predicting Multiple Myeloma Intermediate States**

413 Having demonstrated the generative capacity of Cell-DRL on unperturbed cell state
414 transitions, we tested the method in complex disease scenarios such as multiple
415 myeloma (MM) disease evolution. MM is a bone marrow malignancy resulting from the
416 uncontrolled proliferation of neoplastic plasma cells. Evolution of this blood cancer is
417 characterized by a multi-step process driven by genetic and epigenetic changes, which
418 transform the normal plasma cells through stages of increasing malignancy, including
419 monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance (MGUS), smoldering multiple
420 myeloma (SMM), and ultimately to a high-risk malignant state with myeloma and plasma
421 cell leukemia predominance²⁵.

422 To test Cell-DRL on intermediate MM state reconstruction, we utilized scRNA-seq data
423 from a $\nu\kappa$ *MYC transgenic mouse model^{26,27}. These mice exhibit a progressive
424 accumulation of clonal plasma cells in the bone marrow, mirroring the evolutionary
425 trajectory of human MM (Figure 4A). By sub-setting the *Scd1*/MYC malignant
426 compartment and performing clustering, we identified four major clusters representing
427 different disease states, ranging from early to intermediate and active disease stages
428 (Figure 4B). The malignancy marker *Scd1* and MYC transcript displayed an expression
429 gradient correlating with disease activity, with cluster 1 exhibiting low expression and
430 cluster 0 showing the highest expression (Figure 4C and Extended Data Fig. 9A and B).

431 To train the Cell-DRL agent, we utilized the data from early MM (Cluster 1) and late MM
432 (Cluster 0) as anchoring cell states (Figure 4D and Extended Data Fig. 9D and E). Co-
433 embedding of the generated and the real data indicates that the generated states cover
434 the entire manifold of ground truth MM states including the intermediate states (Figure

435 4E and Extended Data Fig. 9E and F). The reconstruction accuracy is reflected by high
 436 and cluster-specific correlation of real and reconstructed single-cell transcriptomes
 437 (Figure 4F), which is preserved for the subsets of cluster-specific differentially expressed
 438 and highly variable genes (Figure 4F and G).
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Figure 4: Reconstruction of Murine Multiple Myeloma (MM) Tumor Evolution and Patient-Specific Relapse State Trajectory.

- A. Diagram depicting the multistep evolutionary stages of MM tumors.
- B. UMAP representation of the malignant compartment in the Vκ*MYC Transgenic MM Mouse Model, highlighting various stages of MM disease activity in Leiden clusters (MM, Intermediate, and Active MM).
- C. Violinplot displaying the normalized gene expression pattern of the Scd1 malignancy marker across different Leiden clusters, reflecting varying levels of MM disease activity (higher expression values indicate a more malignant state).
- D. UMAP representation for the two-state challenge, presenting early MM (Cluster 1) and active MM (Cluster 0) to the Cell-DRL agent.
- E. Density plot of UMAP representation demonstrating co-localization patterns of real and generated states overlaying the cellular states manifold.
- F. Heatmap illustrating correlation patterns between gene expression of real and generated data in each Leiden cluster.
- G. Barplot indicating Pearson correlation coefficients between the top 150 differentially expressed (DE) genes for real and generated data, and between highly variable genes (HVGs) within Leiden clusters.

463 **Cell-DRL infers novel drivers of human cardiac fibroblast-to-** 464 **cardiomyocyte trans-differentiation**

465 Myocardial infarction (MI) results in functional loss of cardiac muscle cells and impaired
466 overall heart function. Following an infarction event, remodeling processes are initiated,
467 characterized by an extensive inflammatory response. This response leads to the
468 mobilization of innate and adaptive immune cells, notably macrophages, while the
469 damaged tissue undergoes replacement by scar tissue produced from activated
470 fibroblasts leading to functional impairment of the cardiac muscle^{36,37}. A potential for
471 remuscularization of the damaged ventricle to restore cardiac function lies in the direct
472 reprogramming of cardiac fibroblasts into cardiomyocytes, which has been explored in
473 humans and mouse^{38,39,40}. However, the gene expression dynamics governing this
474 process have remained elusive due to the lack of a systematic approach for predicting
475 such trans-differentiation cellular states.

476 To test the capacity of Cell-DRL to predict unseen states on known reprogramming
477 trajectories, we applied our method to scRNA-seq data of murine cardiac reprogramming
478 data⁴¹ and in vitro trans-differentiation from B cells to myeloid cells⁴². In both scenarios,
479 Cell-DRL reconstructed unseen intermediate states from distant anchoring states prior
480 and post-reprogramming with high specificity (Extended Data Fig. 10A-M). In particular,
481 the agent did not generate cells covering aberrant or alternative reprogramming fates in
482 both reprogramming scenarios.

483 To derive a potential trans-differentiation path we applied Cell-DRL to single-cell RNA-
484 seq data of human cardiac fibroblasts from the fibrotic zone of damaged heart tissue of
485 multiple MI patients samples and cardiomyocytes of normal healthy donors^{43,44} (Figure
486 5A and Extended Data Fig. 11A). Through training the Cell-DRL model on these
487 anchoring states, we predicted the unseen intermediate cell states (Figure 5B and
488 Extended Data Fig. 11B and C). To analyze the predicted gene expression dynamics, we
489 performed pseudotime inference and focused on the inferred profiles of differentially
490 expressed genes between clusters (Extended Data Fig. 11D-J). This approach allowed us
491 to stratify the predicted trans-differentiation path into three major transcriptional events,
492 prioritizing the selection of underlying features based on their expression patterns during
493 embryonic development^{45,46} and further supported by prior knowledge^{47,48,49,50} (Figure
494 5C).

495 These events are characterized by the dynamic regulation of three distinct gene modules,
496 comprising transcription factors (TFs), receptors, and ligands (Figure 5D and Extended
497 Data Fig. 11G-J and 14A-D).

498 Initial upregulation of TFs such as *SOX5*, *RUNX1*, and *HEYL* (*Event 1*) was followed by
499 the upregulation of *TEAD4*, *HES5*, *LIN28A*, *ONECUT3*, *ZIC1*, *POU2F3*, *BARX2*, *PAX7*,
500 *SHOX*, and *ELF3* (*Event 2*). Ultimately, commitment to the cardiomyocyte fate coincided
501 with the upregulation of *FHL2* and *ESRRG* (*Event 3*) along with the previously known
502 reprogramming factors *GATA4* and *MEF2C* (Figure 5D)³⁹. Cell-DRL reconstruction using
503 different patient-specific fibroblast populations⁴⁴ as starting states yielded consistent
504 trans-differentiation paths, indicating the robustness of our approach (Extended Data Fig.
505 12E-H and 13A).

506 To experimentally validate the roles of the predicted Events 1 and 2, we induced
507 regulators defining these events in cultured human cardiac fibroblasts (HCF) and
508 measured reprogramming towards the cardiomyocyte fate (Figure 5E, Methods). We first
509 introduced the NOTCH pathway agonist DLL4⁵¹ which activates the Event 1 gene *HEYL*,

510 followed by transduction of lentiviruses encoding Event 2 transcription factors
511 (*HES5/SHOX/TEAD4* and *ONECUT3/LIN28A*). In addition, we introduced the NOTCH
512 pathway agonist DLL1⁵¹ to activate the Event 2 gene *HES5*, in a sequential manner. As a
513 positive control, we compared the reprogramming efficiency attained with the Cell-DRL
514 predicted factors to a cocktail of established human reprogramming factors comprising
515 *MEF2C*, *GATA4*, and *TBX5* (hMGT)⁵².

516 We collected cells for single-nucleus (sn)RNA-seq (Figure 5E, F, and Extended Data
517 Figures 14 and 15) and performed data integration of the *in vitro* reprogrammed states
518 (day 7) with the real anchoring cell state and Cell-DRL generated intermediate cell state
519 data. The analysis revealed co-mapping of the *in vitro* reprogrammed intermediate states
520 with Cell-DRL-generated intermediate states (Figure 5F).

521 After 7 days of reprogramming, the predicted Event 2 led to downregulation of the
522 fibroblast identity markers *COL1A1*, *COL3A1*, *POSTN*, and *FN1* compared to non-
523 treated HCF (control) (Extended Data Fig.13B and 14E), indicating that the cell-of-origin
524 identity program was silenced, an essential step towards successful direct
525 reprogramming to the new cellular state identity. Induction of Event 2 factors further led
526 to the up-regulation of CM progenitor and identity genes (*TNNT1*, *NKX2-5*, and *MYH6*)
527 as well as functional CM markers encoding potassium and calcium channels (*KCNJ2* and
528 *RYR2*) as confirmed by qRT-PCR (Extended Data Fig.13B and 16D). Furthermore, the co-
529 mapping of our *in vitro* scRNA-seq data with the published hMGT reprogramming
530 scRNA-seq data⁵³ showed consistent expression of induced CM (iCM) marker genes
531 (*CMYA5*, *TGFB3*, *CRYAB*, *HSPB2*, *FGL2*, and *JUP*) as well as mature CM genes (Extended
532 Data Fig.15A-E).

533 Since CM markers were only sparsely expressed in our snRNA-seq data, we reasoned
534 that successfully reprogrammed cells were potentially more sensitive to stress during
535 nucleus isolation, as have been reported before⁵⁴, and may not have survived the
536 isolation protocol. We thus performed bulk RNA-seq on day 7 and observed
537 upregulation of cardiac-specific genes, including *NKX2-5*, *TNNI3*, *TNNT1*, *TTN*,
538 *GATA4*, *SOX5*, *MEF2C*, and *CALCA* (Fig. 5G and Extended Data 16 and 17). *NKX2-5* is
539 a key regulator of cardiac identity, and *TNNI3* encodes cardiac troponin I, a critical
540 component for coordinating myocardial contraction⁵⁵. Moreover, ventricular CM
541 markers such as *SOX5*, *EBF1*, and *DLC1*⁴³, potassium channel-related genes (*KCNJ2*,
542 *KCNJ11*, and *KCNJ4*), which contribute to cardiac excitability, as well as *CALCA*, an
543 important modulator of calcium currents in cardiac muscle⁵⁶ were upregulated.
544 Concomitantly, fibroblast markers (*COL3A1*, *COL1A2*, *COL1A1*, *POSTN*) were
545 downregulated. Notably, markers predicted by Cell-DRL (*HES5*, *TEAD4*, *LIN28A*, *SHOX*,
546 *ONECUT3*) showed significant upregulation. We confirmed these expression changes
547 for select markers by smFISH (Methods and Extended Data Fig. 15F).

548 On the protein level, FACS analysis on day 7 of reprogramming with Event 2 factors
549 revealed stronger upregulation of α -actinin and cTNT protein compared to hMGT
550 transduction and control (5H and Extended Data Fig.13C-E). Moreover,
551 immunofluorescence analysis of connexin 43 suggested the formation of gap junction-
552 like structures in the Event 2 condition on day 15 (Extended Data Fig.15G). Finally,
553 reprogrammed cells exhibited a more pronounced mitochondrial network morphology
554 than HCF consistent with CM phenotypes and were positive for α -actinin and titin M-
555 line, suggesting the development of early sarcomere structures in the reprogrammed cells
556 (Figure 5I-J)

557 Together, our experiments demonstrate the potency of de novo Cell-DRL predicted
558 intermediate cellular states and driving factors to enable reprogram HCF toward the CM
559 fate. Our results shed light on the molecular events driving human cardiac fibroblast-to-
560 cardiomyocyte trans-differentiation, thereby providing insights into potential targets for
561 therapeutic interventions. Further exploration of these transcriptional events and
562 regulatory modules *in vivo* may open new avenues for enhancing cardiac regeneration
563 and improving heart function in MI patients.

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570 **Figure 5: Predicting a Novel Trans-differentiation Path (Direct Reprogramming) from**
571 **Human Fibroblasts to Cardiomyocytes.**

- 572 A. UMAP representation of single-nucleus RNA-seq fibroblast and cardiomyocyte populations extracted
573 from the Fibrotic Zone (FZ) of infarcted heart patients. Colors indicate different cell identities.
574 B. UMAP representations illustrating the Cell-DRL novel reconstructed trans-differentiation path between
575 fibroblasts and cardiomyocytes.

- 576 C. UMAP representation displaying the key three transcriptional events regulating the trans-
577 differentiation path and direct reprogramming of fibroblast states to cardiomyocyte states.
- 578 D. Heatmap depicting transcription factors, ligands, and receptors regulating the three key transcriptional
579 events governing the trans-differentiation path.
- 580 E. Schematic representation of the fibroblast-cardiac reprogramming experiment.
- 581 F. Density plot of UMAP representation demonstrating co-localization patterns of the snRNA-seq data of
582 day 7 *in vitro* reprogrammed with the Cell-DRL-generated intermediate states.
- 583 G. The heatmap shows the expression pattern of cardiac and fibroblast marker genes in the *in vitro*
584 experiment Event 2 vs HCF as measured by bulk RNA-seq.
- 585 H. FACS analysis of day 7 reprogrammed cells with antibodies against α -Actinin and cTNT, respectively.
586 Quantification of signals was determined by the log₂ fold change (log₂FC) of each measured sample
587 against the averaged signal intensity of HCF condition. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, and ***p < 0.001.
- 588 I. Representative immunofluorescence staining of reprogrammed cells at day 15, showing α -actinin
589 (green), Mitospy (red), and Titin M-line (magenta).
- 590 J. The mitochondrial network (upper panel) and non-branches (lower panel) quantifications based on
591 Mitospy staining were analyzed using the ImageJ plugin MiNa. Each dot represents one analyzed
592 image. Statistical significance was determined using the Mann-Whitney test for pairwise comparisons
593 between groups. Significant values are as follows: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.
- 594

595 Discussion

596 Many diseases evolve and manifest due to the accumulation of genetic and epigenetic
597 dysregulations throughout our lifetime. The evolution of such diseases is a continuous
598 process, progressing from a healthy state via intermediate dysregulated states toward a
599 full-blown disease state³. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the underlying
600 dynamics of disease evolution and enable early interceptive therapeutic approaches, we
601 would need a dense longitudinal sampling of patient samples. This sampling would
602 allow for stitching together snapshots of sequential cellular states, facilitating the
603 reconstruction of the continuous trajectory. Implementing such an approach is inherently
604 challenging since it would rely on sampling disease-associated processes over the span
605 of numerous years covering the course of disease evolution. Computational approaches
606 for predicting disease trajectories (e.g., Waddington-OT²³, RNA velocity²², scGen²⁴, and
607 CellOracle⁵⁷) fall short when applied to clinically relevant situations because they
608 depend on a sufficiently dense sampling of intermediate states, a feature frequently
609 missing from disease atlases. Here, we introduce Cell-DRL as a deep reinforcement
610 learning agent capable of geometric reasoning on biological manifolds and
611 reconstructing missing cellular states to unveil mechanistic insights into patient-specific
612 intermediate disease paths.

613 Using human samples and mouse models, we validated Cell-DRL across health and
614 disease scenarios. Our results demonstrate the Cell-DRL agent's capacity to reconstruct
615 linear biological processes such as the cell cycle and the epithelial-mesenchymal
616 transition but also the ability to navigate highly non-linear and dynamic processes,
617 exemplified by hematopoiesis. Specifically, the agent accurately reconstructed
618 hematopoietic stem cell and multipotent progenitor states from two distinct progenitor
619 populations, neutrophil and erythroid states, residing on different branches. Pseudo-time
620 analysis underscored the agent's proficiency in identifying the correct temporal sequence
621 of transcriptional events governing hematopoiesis. These examples showcase the
622 capability of Cell-DRL to faithfully reconstruct concealed cellular states, even when
623 residing on non-linear trajectories.

624 In the context of tumor evolution, we tested Cell-DRL using the Vκ*MYC transgenic
625 multiple myeloma (MM) mouse model²⁷ and on primary disease and relapse samples
626 from a human MM patient²⁹. Our findings demonstrate the agent's capacity to reconstruct
627 intermediate MM states, progressively transitioning into fully developed active MM
628 states. Such insights may prove invaluable in customizing therapies to effectively target
629 high-risk cellular states and mitigate the potential for relapse.

630 Finally, we challenged the capabilities of Cell-DRL to reconstruct a trans-differentiation
631 path between two distinct cellular identities, human cardiac fibroblasts, and
632 cardiomyocytes. Cell-DRL predicted a novel direct trans-differentiation path governed
633 by a sequence of three pivotal transcriptional events, and we experimentally demonstrate
634 that inducing predicted core factors controlling these intermediate events achieves a
635 similar induction of the CM fate as reprogramming with an established combination of
636 factors^{52,58,38}. These findings showcase that Cell-DRL facilitates the discovery of novel
637 reprogramming strategies.

638 In its current form, the reconstruction capacity of Cell-DRL relies on the gene-gene
639 covariance structure encoded in the initial and target states and the reconstructed path
640 depends on the distance of the anchoring states defined by the learning bound scores.
641 While Cell-DRL reconstructed the actual HSC state from the erythroid and neutrophil

642 progenitors, it generated a direct reprogramming path connecting mature fibroblasts and
643 cardiomyocytes. In the latter scenario, the covariance structure encoded in the anchoring
644 states likely does not provide sufficient information on the gene programs active in the
645 common developmental progenitor to guide reconstruction via this upstream progenitor
646 state. Extending Cell-DRL by incorporating publicly available scRNA-seq atlases of
647 related biological systems as priors into the learning process may help to guide
648 reconstruction traversing desired cellular states.

649 Orthogonally, we envision that the Cell-DRL's architecture can be naturally extended to
650 integrate additional molecular modalities such as chromatin accessibility and protein
651 expression. Moreover, future extensions of Cell-DRL should accommodate multi-agent
652 learning coupled with dynamics of cell states in tissues to reconstruct entire lineage trees.
653 While Cell-DRL in its current form does not directly inform on the occurrence of a
654 reconstructed path under endogenous circumstances, the Cell-DRL framework can
655 facilitate the incorporation of signaling interactions with the microenvironment as
656 potential drivers of cell state changes, providing insights on the realization of
657 reconstructed cell state transitions in a defined tissue environment.

658 Furthermore, while Cell-DRL faithfully generates intermediate paths connecting defined
659 cellular states, the agent cannot model competition in polyclonal populations, which
660 represents another important direction for extending the Cell-DRL framework.

661 In the long term, such extensions may help to recover the dynamics of inter-cellular
662 crosstalk, enabling the reconstruction of temporal trajectories of tissue architecture and
663 contribute to a holistic understanding of disease processes.

664
665 Thus, Cell-DRL opens new avenues for comprehending biological processes and disease
666 evolution across extended timeframes, even when underlying data is absent. Our
667 approach transcends the mere descriptive analysis of snapshot single-cell genomics data.
668 We envision Cell-DRL as a facilitator for uncovering patient-specific intermediate
669 disease paths. Such predictions could offer promising avenues for early disease detection
670 and intervention. Cell-DRL holds the promise to improve predictive and personalized
671 medicine, while also pushing the boundaries in the field of regenerative medicine.

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674

675 **Methods**

676

677 **Reconstruction of Intermediate Disease Paths on Biological Manifolds:**

678 To model the progression of cellular states within a biological process, we represent the
679 underlying biological space of all potential cellular states as a manifold \mathbf{M} , where each
680 point corresponds to a cellular state defined by its gene expression profile (Figure 1C).
681 Some of these states are observed through single-cell genomics data (as cell atlases).
682 However, the intermediate states are missing from such biological manifold. Such
683 biological processes are governed by a set of Markov Decision Processes (MDPs), the
684 goal of the Cell-DRL Agent is to reconstruct and generate the intermediate cellular paths
685 on this manifold that reflect the evolution from one cellular state to another over time.

686

687 **Cell-DRL algorithm overview:**

688 Cell-DRL is a deep reinforcement learning agent capable of interacting in the Cell-DRL
689 environment, generating actions, and reconstructing cellular states in the gene
690 expression space of the biological manifold \mathbf{M} . We represent a given cellular state as \mathbf{s}
691 $\in \mathbb{R}^{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{j}}$, with cell index $\mathbf{x} = 1, \dots, \mathbf{C}$ and gene index $\mathbf{j} = 1, \dots, \mathbf{G}$. We denote the initial
692 cellular state as $\mathbf{S}^i \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{j}}$ and the target cellular state of interest as $\mathbf{S}^f \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{j}}$. The
693 goal of the Cell-DRL agent is to generate a sequence of intermediate cellular states
694 $\mathbf{S}^{\text{gen}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{j}}$ representing an intermediate path connecting two anchoring cellular
695 states ($\mathbf{S}^i, \mathbf{S}^f$).

696

697

698 **Cell-DRL Environment:**

699 To find the missing cellular state \mathbf{S}^{gen} , we designed a deep reinforcement learning
700 algorithm. In the following, we describe four key components of the Cell-DRL
701 environment (Fig 1A and S1C):

702

703

- 704 1. Action Generator and Controller (**AGC**) Unit.
- 705 2. Observation space (**O**).
- 706 3. Reward function (**R**).
- 707 4. Policy network ($\pi\theta$).

708

709

710 We designed our Cell-DRL environment to be represented as an infinite-horizon Markov
711 decision process (MDP)⁷. The MDP is defined by a tuple $(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{P}, \mathbf{r})$, where \mathbf{S} represents
712 a complete description of the environment state and \mathbf{A} represents a continuous action
713 space in the environment. The transition probability \mathbf{P} represents the probability density
714 of the next state $\mathbf{st}+1 \in \mathbf{S}$ given the current state of the environment $\mathbf{st} \in \mathbf{S}$ and the
715 action $\mathbf{at} \in \mathbf{A}$.

716

717 We define a trajectory τ as a sequence of states and actions in the environment through
718 \mathbf{H} steps:

719

$$720 \quad \tau^{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{s}_0, \mathbf{a}_0, \mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{a}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{\mathbf{H}}, \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{H}}$$

721

722 The transition from one cellular state to another is governed by a stochastic state
723 transition function:

724

$$725 \quad \mathbf{st+1} \sim P \cdot | \mathbf{st}, \mathbf{at}$$

726

727 The actions are generated by the agent according to the policy network π_{θ} which is
728 parametrized by θ :

729

$$730 \quad \mathbf{at} \sim \pi_{\theta} \cdot | \mathbf{st}$$

731

732 The environment releases a reward \mathbf{rt} after each transition which is dependent on the
733 current state of the environment, the actions taken, and the environment's next state
734 given the reward function \mathbf{R} :

735

$$736 \quad \mathbf{rt} = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{st} + \mathbf{1})$$

737

738

739 The goal of the agent is to find the parameters θ of the optimum policy $\pi_{\theta}(\mathbf{at} | \mathbf{st})$ by
740 maximizing the expected total reward $\mathbf{J}\pi$ summed over the trajectory,

741

$$742 \quad \mathbf{J}\pi = \max_{\pi} \mathbf{E}t = \mathbf{0} \mathbf{H} \gamma t \mathbf{R} \mathbf{st}, \mathbf{at}, \mathbf{st} + \mathbf{1} | \pi$$

743

744

745

746 where the horizon parameter \mathbf{H} represents the number of steps on each trajectory:

747

748

$$749 \quad \pi_{\theta} = \operatorname{argmax}_{\pi} \mathbf{J}\pi$$

750

751

752 We extend the reward objective to an infinite-horizon discounted return $\mathbf{R}(\tau)$ over a
753 trajectory, with a discounting factor $\gamma \in \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}$:

754

755

$$756 \quad \mathbf{R}(\tau) = \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t \mathbf{rt}$$

757

758 where $\gamma < \mathbf{1}$ induces a discount effect on the overall return.

759

760

761

762 **Actions Generator and Controller (AGC) unit:**

763 To enable our agent to intervene with actions within the Cell-DRL action space \mathbf{A} , we
764 designed a novel mechanism for generating and controlling cellular states in the gene
765 expression space.

766

767 The (AGC) is composed of two Sub-Units:

768

769 I. Gen-Unit.

770 II. Do-Unit.

771

772

773 I. **Gen-Unit:**

774 We designed the Cell-DRL Gen-Unit to generate cellular states in gene expression space.

775 The generation process starts with concatenating \mathbf{si} and \mathbf{sf} into a matrix $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{x,j}$:

776

777

$$\mathbf{M} = [\mathbf{si} \ \mathbf{sf}]$$

778

779 We push the \mathbf{M} matrix to a standard data pre-processing unit (S1C, implementation
780 details); to perform log-normalization (using size factor 10^4 molecules for each cell) and
781 scale the gene expression values for each gene (z-score transformation)⁵⁹. The AGC unit
782 transposes the pre-processed \mathbf{M} and calculates the gene-gene covariance matrix $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in$
783 $\mathbb{R}^{j,j}$:

784

$$\mathbf{\Sigma} = \mathit{cov}(\mathbf{M}^T)$$

785

786

787

788 To extract the orthogonal axes of gene expression variability characteristic of the gene
789 regulatory networks governing \mathbf{si} and \mathbf{sf} , the AGC performs singular value
790 decomposition (SVD) on $\mathbf{\Sigma}$,

791

$$\mathbf{\Sigma} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{V}^T$$

792

793

794 where

795

796 a) $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{j,f}$ represents the left-singular vectors of $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ with \mathbf{f} decomposed
797 factors,

798 b) $\mathbf{\Lambda} \in \mathbb{R}^{j,j}$ represents the singular-value diagonal matrix, and

799 c) $\mathbf{V}^T \in \mathbb{R}^{f,j}$ represents the right-singular vectors of $\mathbf{\Sigma}$.

800

801 The Gen-Unit generates new cellular states \mathbf{s}_{gen} by sampling from a multivariate
802 gaussian distribution $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{x_{gen},f}$,

803

804

$$\mathbf{X} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_{gen}, \sigma_{gen})$$

805

806 where the two parameters μ_{gen} and σ_{gen} control mean and standard deviation of
 807 the generated cellular state \mathbf{s}_{gen} and each dimension implements an action on one of
 808 the factors. The chosen dimension x_{gen} controls the number of generated cells.

809
 810

$$\Psi = \mathbf{U} \cdot \Lambda + \zeta$$

$$\mathbf{s}_{gen} = \mathbf{X} \cdot \Psi^T + \mu_j \max \mu_j$$

813

814 Since \mathbf{U} describes the direction of Σ matrix's underlying maximum action, we introduced
 815 ζ as a scaling parameter for Λ , to control the action magnitude. Finally, μ_j represents the
 816 mean gene expression of the two cellular states \mathbf{M} , which we "max" normalize it in \mathbf{s}_{gen} .

817

818

819 II. Do-unit:

820 We introduced Do-unit to enable the agent to control the generated cellular states in
 821 gene expression space via **do** operation on the (μ_{gen}, σ_{gen} and ζ) Gen-Unit
 822 parameters,

823

824

$$cgn \sim \text{do}(\mu_{gen} = 0, \sigma_{gen} > 0)$$

825

826

$$coe \sim \text{do}(\mu_{gen} > 0, \sigma_{gen} > 0)$$

827

828

$$ckd \sim \text{do}(\mu_{gen} < 0, \sigma_{gen} > 0)$$

829

830

$$Pertsv \sim \text{do}(\zeta > 0)$$

831

832

833

834 where cgn, coe or ckd represent possible outcomes of the Do-unit, i.e., gaussian noise,
 835 overexpression, or knockdown, respectively, for the newly generated cellular state \mathbf{s}_{gen} .
 836 In addition, $Pertsv$ perturbs the singular values by interventions through tuning the
 837 scaling parameter ζ .

838

839 The task of the agent is to find the controller parameters (μ_{gen}, σ_{gen} and ζ) of optimum
 840 policy. Ultimately, the optimum policy will guide the agent to predict a sequence of
 841 actions and to reconstruct \mathbf{S}_{gen} in H steps for a given τH . Before describing the policy
 842 network, we will introduce the observation space and outline how the agent observes
 843 the environment.

844

845 **The Observation Space:**

846 The Cell-DRL observation space is a cellular state manifold representing all possible
847 configurations of a cell (Fig 1A). The agent can visit and reconstruct certain regions of
848 interest within this space. We termed such regions of the observation space
849 Reconstruction Field (RF) (Fig 1E).

850

851 To guide the agent and enable gaining a sense of directionality and distances in the
852 Reconstruction Field, we developed four key parts in the Cell-DRL observation space:

853

- 854 I. State Observation (**O**).
- 855 II. Cellular States Distance (**CSD**).
- 856 III. Learning Bound Scores (**LBS**).
- 857 IV. Cellular State Loss (**CSL**).

858

859

860 I. **Single Observation (O):**

861 We summarize a given cellular state **s** into a single observation **O** according to the
862 following equation,

863

864

$$\mathbf{O} = \text{SoftMax}(\text{MGA}(\mathbf{s}))$$

865

866 where we calculate the median gene activity (MGA) of a given cellular state **s** and
867 rescale it via SoftMax function to *j-dimensional* output ranging from [0,1] which is
868 summing to 1.

869

870

871 II. **Cellular States Distance (CSD):**

872 First, we calculate a Cellular States Distance (CSD) between the initial cellular state
873 observation \mathbf{O}_i and the target cellular observation \mathbf{O}_f :

874

$$\text{CSD } \mathbf{O}_i \mathbf{O}_f = 1 - \text{scos} \mathbf{O}_i \mathbf{O}_f \times \vartheta \text{DKL} \mathbf{O}_i \parallel \mathbf{O}_f$$

875

876 The **CSD** is composed of two terms:

877

- 880 a) Cosine similarity term: $1 - \text{scos} \mathbf{O}_i \mathbf{O}_f$
- 881 b) Kullback-Leibler divergence term: $\text{DKL} \mathbf{O}_i \parallel \mathbf{O}_f$

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884 The parameter ϑ defines the importance of the **DKL** terms to the **CSD**.

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892 III. **Learning bound scores (LBS)**

893 The Learning bound scores (LBS) define the boundaries of the cellular state
 894 reconstruction field (Fig 1E), comprising four key cellular bound scores,

895

$$896 \quad \mathbf{RBmin} = \mathbf{CSD} \times \alpha,$$

897

$$898 \quad \mathbf{RBmax} = \mathbf{CSD} \times \beta,$$

899

$$900 \quad \mathbf{TBmax} = \mathbf{CSD} \times \gamma,$$

901

$$902 \quad \mathbf{TBmin} = \omega$$

903

904

905 where α controls the minimum reward bound \mathbf{RBmin} , β controls the maximum reward
 906 bound \mathbf{RBmax} , γ controls the maximum trajectory bound \mathbf{TBmax} and ω controls the
 907 minimum trajectory bound \mathbf{TBmin} .

908

909

910

911 **IV. Cellular State Loss (CSL):**

912 We introduce the Cellular state loss (CSL) to enable the agent to learn the distances
 913 between generated and target cellular state observations:

914

$$915 \quad \mathbf{CSL} \mathbf{Ogen} \mathbf{Of} = \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{scos} \mathbf{O} \mathbf{i} \mathbf{Of} \times \vartheta \mathbf{DKL} \mathbf{O} \mathbf{gen} \parallel \mathbf{Of}$$

$$916 \quad \quad \quad - \lambda \mathbf{POgen} \times \log \mathbf{POgen}$$

917

918

919 The CSL is composed of three terms:

920

921 a) Cosine similarity term: $\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{scos} \mathbf{O} \mathbf{i} \mathbf{Of}$

922 b) Kullback-Leibler divergence term: $\mathbf{DKL} \mathbf{O} \mathbf{i} \parallel \mathbf{Of}$

923 c) Entropy regularization term

924

925

926 \mathbf{Ogen} and \mathbf{Of} represent a generated observation and a target state observation,
 927 respectively. The ϑ and λ parameters define the weights of the \mathbf{DKL} and entropy
 928 regulation terms.

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936 **Reward Function:**

937 The reward function of the environment depends on the current cellular state
 938 observations and the \mathbf{CSL} incurred by the newly generated cellular state,

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$$R(s, a, st + 1) = \rho + (1 - CSL)a$$

where ρ is defining the reward signal and a is the reward coefficient. We condition the agent to get *positive or negative* rewards given the **CSL**:

$$R(s, a, st + 1) = rt = \rho + (1 - CSL)a, \quad \text{if } CSL \geq RBmin \wedge CSL \leq RBmax$$
$$rt = -1, \quad \text{otherwise}$$

If the **CSL** is between **RBmin** and **RBmax**, we reinforce such behavior, and the agent receives a *positive* **rt**. In contrast, if our agent exceeds the reward bounds, the agent receives a *negative* **rt**.

Furthermore, we introduced a termination condition **T** with a **done** signal to the Cell-DRL environment, which depends on **TBmax** and **TBmin** as well as the number of steps, for a given cellular state trajectory τ_H . **n** starts at $n = H - 1$ and is decreased by one at each step:

$$T(CSL) = done = True, \quad \text{if } CSL \geq TBmax$$
$$done = True, \quad \text{if } CSL \leq TBmin$$
$$done = True, \quad \text{if } n \leq 0$$
$$= False, \quad \text{otherwise}$$

966 **Policy Network:**

967 The Cell-DRL policy π_{θ} is parametrized by a neural network and optimized via gradient
968 ascent, where the α parameter controls the learning rate:

969

$$970 \quad \theta \leftarrow \theta + \alpha \nabla_{\theta} \mathbb{E} \pi_{\theta} R(\tau)$$

971

972 The gradient tries to *increase* the probability of paths with *positive* r_t values and *decrease*
973 the probability of paths with *negative* r_t values. We perform Monte Carlo sampling of N
974 trajectories and run the policy π_{θ}^{60} . Then, we fit a multilayer perceptron (MLP) to
975 estimate the return and improve the policy iteratively:

976

977

$$978 \quad \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_{i,t} | s_{i,t}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_t \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_{i,t} | s_{i,t}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_t r_{i,t} \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_{i,t} | s_{i,t})$$

979

980

981 In addition to optimizing for the standard maximum reward objective, we considered
982 the Soft-Actor-Critic maximum entropy objective¹⁰:

983

984

$$985 \quad \mathcal{H} \pi_{\cdot} | s_t = \mathbb{E} a \sim \pi(\cdot | s) [-\log(\pi(a | s))]$$

986

987

988 The entropy term \mathcal{H} controls the stochastic behavior of Cell-DRL policies π_{θ} . The
989 maximum entropy objective enables our agent to alternate between exploration and
990 exploitation phases during training:

991

992

$$993 \quad \pi_{\theta} = \operatorname{argmax}_{\pi} \mathbb{E} \tau \sim \pi \quad t = 0 \infty \gamma t R_{st}, a_t, s_t + 1 + \alpha \mathcal{H} \pi_{\cdot} | s_t$$

994

995

996 The agent gets rewards proportional to the entropy term \mathcal{H} in our policy π_{θ} , and the α
997 parameter determines the relative importance of the \mathcal{H} given the reward at each time
998 step. Higher α corresponds to more exploration and lower α corresponds to more
999 exploitation.

1000

1001 **Optimal Intermediate Paths (OIP):**

1002 To define the plausible intermediate paths given the predicted actions, we developed
1003 the Optimum Intermediate Paths (OIP) concept. The agent generates actions from the
1004 trained policy network $\pi\theta$. The predicted action parameters μ_{gen}, σ_{gen} and ζ values
1005 are pushed to the Gen-Unit. The **CSL** is calculated for each path τH and a matrix with
1006 k sampled realizations and cellular state losses $P_{k,n}$ is constructed accordingly:

1007
1008

$$P_{k,n} = CSL (G, at)$$

1009
1010
1011

1012 The trained agent generates k realizations representing generated paths with H steps
1013 where each path connects the same two anchoring cellular states (S_i, S_f). Ultimately,
1014 to define the optimal paths OCP_i , we calculate the quantiles Q_j for the $P_{k,n}$ matrix,

1015
1016

$$OCP_i(S_{gen}, S_f) = Q_j (P_{k,n}, j)$$

1017
1018
1019

1020 where $0 \leq j \leq 1$ to stratify paths according to the **CSL** distribution:

1021
1022

$$\begin{aligned} OCP_i(S_{gen}, S_f) = \text{path} &= \text{Min}, & \text{if } j = 0.1 & \text{ path} = \text{Optimum}, & \text{if } j \\ &= 0.5 & \text{ path} = \text{Max}, & \text{if } j = 0.9 & \text{ path} \\ &= \text{Other}, & \text{otherwise} & \end{aligned}$$

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1030 **Plausibility Score via Bures-Wasserstein Distance**

1031 To further validate the reconstructed intermediate paths, we introduce a "Plausibility
1032 Score" based on the Bures-Wasserstein distance²⁰. This score measures how closely the
1033 covariance matrix of a generated path aligns with that of observed single-cell large
1034 atlases, thus assessing the likelihood that the generated path represents a biologically
1035 plausible cellular state.

1036 Given a reference covariance matrix $\Sigma_{\text{Reference}}$ (from observed single-cell large atlas) and
1037 a covariance matrix $\Sigma_{\text{Generated}}$ from Cell-DRL generated cellular states' paths, the Bures-
1038 Wasserstein distance $d_{\text{BW}}(\Sigma_{\text{Generated}}, \Sigma_{\text{Reference}})$ is computed as:

$$1039 \quad d_{\text{BW}}(\Sigma_{\text{gen}}, \Sigma_{\text{ref}}) = \sqrt{\text{Tr}(\Sigma_{\text{gen}}) + \text{Tr}(\Sigma_{\text{ref}}) - 2 \sqrt{\text{Tr}(\Sigma_{\text{gen}} \Sigma_{\text{ref}})}}$$

1040 To make these distances comparable, we normalize them across all generated paths:
1041

$$1042 \quad d_{\text{norm}} = \frac{d_{\text{BW}}(\Sigma_{\text{Generated}}, \Sigma_{\text{Reference}}) - d_{\text{min}}}{d_{\text{max}} - d_{\text{min}}}$$

1043 where d_{min} , d_{max} , and d_{norm} are the minimum, maximum, and normalized Bures-
1044 Wasserstein distances observed among all paths, respectively. The Plausibility Score P
1045 is then defined as:

$$1046 \quad P = 1 - d_{\text{norm}}$$

1047 A higher P indicates a greater similarity between the generated path and the reference
1048 atlas, suggesting that the path is more likely to "exist" in nature. Conversely, a lower P
1049 suggests that the generated path is less plausible. This score provides a quantitative
1050 measure for evaluating the biological relevance of the reconstructed paths within the
1051 Cell-DRL framework.

1052

1053 **Linear Interpolation in Variational Autoencoder (VAE) Latent Space:**

1054 To explore linear interpolations in the latent space of a VAE model, we define the
1055 interpolate-VAE function. This function takes as input two gene expression matrices, \mathbf{X}_1
1056 and \mathbf{X}_2 , representing the initial and target cellular states. It encodes \mathbf{X}_1 and \mathbf{X}_2 through the
1057 encoder network to obtain their respective mean and log variance and then uses the
1058 reparametrization trick to sample latent variables \mathbf{Z}_1 and \mathbf{Z}_2 .

1059 To interpolate between \mathbf{Z}_1 and \mathbf{Z}_2 , a range of weights from 0 to 1 in steps of 0.1 is used.
1060 For each weight, the function computes an interpolated latent variable $\mathbf{Z}_{\text{inter}}$:

1061

$$1062 \quad \mathbf{Z}_{\text{inter}} = (1 - w) \cdot \mathbf{Z}_1 + w \cdot \mathbf{Z}_2$$

1063

1064 where $\mathbf{Z}_{\text{inter}}$ is the interpolated latent variable, \mathbf{Z}_1 is the latent variable for the initial
1065 state, \mathbf{Z}_2 is the latent variable for the target state and w is the interpolation weight.

1066 The function decodes the concatenated intermediate reconstructions $\mathbf{Z}_{\text{inter}}$ through the
1067 decoder network to reconstruct the full gene expression space $\mathbf{X}_{\text{inter}}$ of the interpolated
1068 $\mathbf{Z}_{\text{inter}}$. Afterwards, we created an *anndata* object with the concatenated $\mathbf{X}_{\text{inter}}$ and $\mathbf{Z}_{\text{inter}}$ of

1069 the intermediate states data. For clustering and generating UMAPs, we run
1070 `sc.pp.neighbors(use_rep="VAE_Z")` on the concatenated Z_{inter} and computed `sc.tl.umap`
1071 (`min_dist=0.1`) and `sc.tl.leiden(key_added="VAE_Z_Clusters", resolution=0.5)`.

1072

1073 **Data sets and preprocessing**

1074

1075 **Nestorowa et al. cell cycle scRNA-seq data**

1076 The murine hematopoietic progenitors' data (Nestorowa et al., 2016)¹³ was downloaded
1077 from the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus under the accession number (GSE147405),
1078 and a list of cell cycle markers⁶¹ where used. We used Scanpy functions for the
1079 preprocessing steps. First, we filtered out low-quality cells using
1080 `'sc.pp.filter_cells(min_genes=200)'` and genes with low expression in less than three cells
1081 using `'sc.pp.filter_genes(min_cells=3).'` Then, we performed data log normalization with
1082 `'sc.pp.normalize_per_cell(counts_per_cell_after=1e4)'` and applied `'sc.pp.log1p(adata)'`
1083 to log-transform the data. Subsequently, we scaled the data using
1084 `'sc.pp.scale(max_value=5).'`

1085

1086 We selected cell cycle genes and performed dimensionality reduction with `'sc.tl.pca()'`
1087 to reduce the data to its principal components. To identify local neighborhoods of cells,
1088 we computed a neighborhood graph using `'sc.pp.neighbors(n_neighbors=10,`
1089 `n_pcs=20)'` and ran the UMAP function using `'sc.tl.umap()'` for further visualization.

1090

1091 For the identification of initial and target states, we utilized the Cell-DRL function
1092 `'celldrv.select_cellular_states'` with the parameter `'select_by="phase"'`. We chose
1093 `'Initial_State = "G1"'` to represent the G1 phase and `'Terminal_State = "G2M"'` to represent
1094 the G2/M phase."

1095

1096 After the Cell-DRL training step, the agent generates predicted cellular states, which we
1097 then concatenate with the real data. To prepare the concatenated data, we used
1098 `'sc.pp.scale(max_value=5)'` for scaling the generated data. Next, we applied the Cell-
1099 DRL function `'celldrv.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=20, min_dist=0.5)'` to
1100 perform dimensionality reduction and used UMAP for visualization of the concatenated
1101 object.

1102

1103

1104 **Cook et al. EMT scRNA-seq data**

1105 The EMT data from Cook et al.¹⁵ was downloaded from the NCBI Gene Expression
1106 Omnibus under the accession number (GSE147405), and the EMT signature gene set was
1107 downloaded from GSEA signatures lists ([https://www.gsea-
1108 msigdb.org/gsea/msigdb/cards/HALLMARK_EPITHELIAL_MESENCHYMAL_TRANSITION](https://www.gsea-msigdb.org/gsea/msigdb/cards/HALLMARK_EPITHELIAL_MESENCHYMAL_TRANSITION.html)
1109 [N.html](https://www.gsea-msigdb.org/gsea/msigdb/cards/HALLMARK_EPITHELIAL_MESENCHYMAL_TRANSITION.html)). We performed data preprocessing using the Cell-DRL function
1110 `'celldrv.pp_sc_object(min_genes=200, min_cells=3, min_counts=0, n_HVGs=3000,`
1111 `max_scale_value=10)'`. Subsequently, we applied dimensionality reduction using the
1112 function `'celldrv.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=50, min_dist=0.45)'`.

1113

1114 For the identification of initial and target states, we utilized the Cell-DRL function
1115 `'celldrv.select_cellular_states'` with the parameter `'select_by="Time"'`. Specifically, we

1116 selected 'Initial_State = '0d'' to represent day 0 and 'Terminal_State = '3d'' to represent
1117 day 3 data.

1118

1119 After the Cell-DRL training step, the agent generates predicted cellular states, which we
1120 then concatenate with the real data. To prepare the concatenated data, we used
1121 'sc.pp.scale(max_value=10)' for scaling the generated data. Next, we applied the Cell-
1122 DRL function 'celldrl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=20, n_pcs=50, min_dist=0.5)' to
1123 perform additional dimensionality reduction. We then utilized UMAP for visualization
1124 of the concatenated object.

1125

1126 **Tusi et al. murine haematopoiesis progenitor scRNA-seq data**

1127 The murine hematopoietic progenitor data¹⁸ were downloaded from GEO with accession
1128 code (GSE89754). First, we removed mitochondrial genes (mt*), ribosomal genes (Rpl*,
1129 Rps*), as well as genes with Gm-identifiers (Gm*). Then, we performed data
1130 preprocessing using the Cell-DRL function 'celldrl.pp_sc_object(min_genes=200,
1131 min_cells=3, min_counts=1000, n_HVGs=3000, max_scale_value=10)'.
1132

1133 Subsequently, we applied dimensionality reduction using the function
1134 'celldrl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=50, min_dist=0.45)'.
1135

1136

1137 For the identification of initial and target states, we utilized the Cell-DRL function
1138 'celldrl.select_cellular_states' with the parameter 'select_by="Clusters"'. Specifically, we
1139 selected 'Initial_State = '1' to represent cluster 1 data, and 'Terminal_State = '2' to
1140 represent cluster 2 data. For more distanced clusters scenario, we selected 'Initial_State
1141 = '5' to represent cluster 5 data, and 'Terminal_State = '7' to represent cluster 7 data. For
1142 the bifurcation scenario, we selected cluster '0' as the root cellular state and cluster '5'
1143 and '7' as the terminal state.

1144

1145 After the Cell-DRL training step, the agent generates predicted cellular states, which we
1146 then concatenate with the real data. To prepare the concatenated data, we used
1147 'sc.pp.scale(max_value=5)' for scaling the generated data. Next, we applied the Cell-
1148 DRL function 'celldrl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=50, min_dist=0.5)' to
1149 perform additional dimensionality reduction. We then utilized UMAP for the
1150 visualization of the concatenated object.

1151

1151 **Croucher et al. in-vivo a Vκ*MYC transgenic MM mouse model scRNA-seq data**

1152 We downloaded the data of the Croucher et al. study²⁷ from NCBI Gene Expression
1153 Omnibus under accession number (GSE134370). For the initial data preprocessing, we
1154 used the Cell-DRL function 'celldrl.pp_sc_object(min_genes=200, min_cells=3,
1155 min_counts=0, n_HVGs=3000, max_scale_value=10)'. Then, we applied
1156 dimensionality reduction using the function 'celldrl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10,
1157 n_pcs=50, min_dist=0.45)' and clustering with 'sc.tl.leiden(resolution=1)'. The B cell
1158 lineage clusters (27, 6, and 10), which represent CD19⁺ cells, were extracted for further
1159 downstream analyses.

1160

1161 Next, we proceeded with the B cell lineage data using the Cell-DRL function
1162 'celldrl.pp_sc_object(min_genes=200, min_cells=3, min_counts=0, n_HVGs=3000,

1163 max_scale_value=10)'. Subsequently, we applied dimensionality reduction using the
1164 function 'cell2drl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=25, min_dist=1)' and clustering
1165 with 'sc.tl.leiden(resolution=0.1)'. We defined four major clusters reflecting the disease's
1166 initial and intermediate active MM states.

1167

1168 For the identification of initial and target states, we utilized the Cell-DRL function
1169 'cell2drl.select_cellular_states' with the parameter 'select_by="leiden"'. Specifically, we
1170 selected 'Initial_State = 2' to represent initial MM data and 'Terminal_State = 1' to
1171 represent active MM data.

1172

1173 After the Cell-DRL training step, the agent generates predicted cellular states, which we
1174 then concatenate with the real data. To prepare the concatenated data, we used
1175 'sc.pp.scale(max_value=10)' for scaling the generated data. Next, we applied the Cell-
1176 DRL function 'cell2drl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=50, min_dist=0.5)' to
1177 perform additional dimensionality reduction. Finally, we utilized UMAP for the
1178 visualization of the concatenated object.

1179

1180 **Liu et al. MM Human patient sample scRNA-seq data**

1181 We downloaded the data of the Liu et al. study²⁹ from
1182 (<https://www.weizmann.ac.il/sites/3CA/hematologic>) and extracted the sc-RNAseq data
1183 of patient ID number 27522. We further extracted the plasma cell compartment,
1184 reflecting the tumor activity of the patient over four different time points. Then, we started
1185 to perform data preprocessing using the Cell-DRL function
1186 'cell2drl.pp_sc_object(min_genes=200, min_cells=3, min_counts=1000, n_HVGs=3000,
1187 max_scale_value=10)'. Subsequently, we applied dimensionality reduction using the
1188 function 'cell2drl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=20, min_dist=1)'. For the
1189 identification of initial and target states, we utilized the Cell-DRL function
1190 'cell2drl.select_cellular_states' with the parameter 'select_by="sample"'. Specifically, we
1191 selected 'Initial_State = 27522_Primary' to represent the primary MM data timepoint and
1192 'Terminal_State = 27522_Relapse-2' to represent Relapse-2 MM data timepoint.

1193

1194 After the Cell-DRL training step, the agent generated the predicted cellular states, which
1195 we then concatenate with the real data. To prepare the concatenated data, we used
1196 'sc.pp.scale(max_value=10)' for scaling the generated data. Next, we applied the Cell-
1197 DRL function 'cell2drl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=50, min_dist=1)' to
1198 perform additional dimensionality reduction. Finally, we utilized UMAP for the
1199 visualization of the concatenated object.

1200

1201 **Stone et al. Murine Cardiac time course reprogramming scRNA-seq data**

1202 We downloaded the data of the Stone et al. study⁴¹ from NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus
1203 under accession number (GSE131328). For the initial data preprocessing, we used the
1204 Cell-DRL function 'cell2drl.pp_sc_object(min_genes=200, min_cells=3, min_counts=0,
1205 n_HVGs=3000, max_scale_value=10)'. Then, we applied dimensionality reduction
1206 using the function 'cell2drl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=20, min_dist=0.45)'
1207 and clustering with 'sc.tl.leiden(resolution=0.4)'.
1208 For the identification of initial and target states, we utilized the Cell-DRL function
1209 'cell2drl.select_cellular_states' with the parameter 'select_by="leiden"'. Specifically, we

1209

1210 selected 'Initial_State =4' to represent initial murine fibroblast data and 'Terminal_State
1211 = 3' to represent iCM state data.

1212 After the Cell-DRL training step, the agent generates predicted cellular states, which we
1213 then concatenate with the real data. To prepare the concatenated data, we used
1214 'sc.pp.scale(max_value=10)' for scaling the generated data. Next, we applied the Cell-
1215 DRL function 'cell_drl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=50, min_dist=0.5)' to
1216 perform additional dimensionality reduction. Finally, we utilized UMAP for the
1217 visualization of the concatenated object.

1218

1219 **Francesconi et al. B-cells trans-differentiation to induced macrophages scRNA-seq data**

1220 We downloaded the data of Francesconi et al.⁴² from NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus
1221 under accession number (GSE112004). For the initial data preprocessing, we used the
1222 Cell-DRL function 'cell_drl.pp_sc_object(min_genes=200, min_cells=3, min_counts=0,
1223 n_HVGs=10000, max_scale_value=10)'. Then, we applied dimensionality reduction
1224 using the function 'cell_drl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=20, min_dist=0.45)'
1225 and clustering with 'sc.tl.leiden(resolution=1.5)'.

1226 For the identification of initial and target states, we utilized the Cell-DRL function
1227 'cell_drl.select_cellular_states' with the parameter 'select_by="cell_type"'. Specifically,
1228 we selected 'Initial_State =B_cell' to represent initial B cells data and 'Terminal_State =
1229 Day_4_trans' to represent induced macrophage state data.

1230 After the Cell-DRL training step, the agent generates predicted cellular states, which we
1231 then concatenate with the real data. To prepare the concatenated data, we used
1232 'sc.pp.scale(max_value=10)' for scaling the generated data. Next, we applied the Cell-
1233 DRL function 'cell_drl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=50, min_dist=0.5)' to
1234 perform additional dimensionality reduction. Finally, we utilized UMAP for the
1235 visualization of the concatenated object.

1236

1237 **Kuppe et al. human myocardial infarction scRNA-seq data**

1238 We downloaded the scRNA-seq data⁶² from the Zenodo data archive
1239 (<https://zenodo.org/record/6578553>) and extracted the Fibroblast populations from the
1240 fibrotic zone (FZ) areas. Also, we downloaded healthy donors' ventricular
1241 cardiomyocyte data from (<https://www.heartcellatlas.org/v1.html>) and extracted the
1242 'Harvard-Nuclei' batch for further processing⁴³. Then, we started to perform data
1243 preprocessing using the Cell-DRL function 'cell_drl.pp_sc_object(min_genes=200,
1244 min_cells=3, min_counts=0, n_HVGs=8000, max_scale_value=10)'. Subsequently, we
1245 applied dimensionality reduction using the function
1246 'cell_drl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=20, min_dist=0.5)'.

1247

1248 For the identification of initial and target states, we utilized the Cell-DRL function
1249 'cell_drl.select_cellular_states' with the parameter 'select_by="cell_type_original"'.
1250 Specifically, we selected 'Initial_State = Fibroblast' to represent the Fibroblast population
1251 data and 'Terminal_State = Cardiomyocyte' to represent the Cardiomyocyte population
1252 data.

1253

1254 After the Cell-DRL training step, the agent generated the predicted cellular states, which
1255 we then concatenated with the real data. To prepare the concatenated data, we used
1256 'sc.pp.scale(max_value=10)' for scaling the generated data. Next, we applied the Cell-

1257 DRL function 'celldrl.dim_reduction(n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=35, min_dist=0.5)' to
1258 perform additional dimensionality reduction. Finally, we utilized UMAP for the
1259 visualization of the concatenated object.

1260

1261 **Gastrulation Data Processing**

1262 We obtained single-cell RNA-seq data of mouse gastrulation and early organogenesis⁶³
1263 from the MouseGastrulationData repository
1264 (https://github.com/MarioniLab/EmbryoTimecourse2018/blob/master/download/download_ad.sh). After loading the data into an anndata object, we performed filtering, scaling (up
1265 to max_scale_value=10), and selected 3,000 highly variable genes (HVGs) using the
1266 celldrl.pp_sc_object function. We reduced dimensionality via celldrl.dim_reduction
1267 (n_neighbors=10, n_pcs=50, min_dist=0.45), followed by cluster assignment using
1268 Leiden (sc.tl.leiden, resolution=0.7). Four pairs of initial-to-terminal cell clusters were
1269 then specified (e.g., Epiblast (cluster 25) to Primitive Streak (cluster 9)) via
1270 celldrl.select_cellular_states to train independent Cell-DRL agents. Each agent generated
1271 cellular states for different germ layers. The resulting agent-generated cell states were
1272 concatenated into a single AnnData object. We integrated these generated states with
1273 the original data and repeated dimensionality reduction on the combined dataset. This
1274 final step allowed direct comparison between real and generated cells, facilitating
1275 validation of the reconstructed germ layers.
1276

1277

1278 **Pseudotime and differential expression analyses:**

1279 We performed pseudotime inference using Scanpy's diffusion pseudotime function
1280 'sc.tl.dpt(n_dcs=3)'. Additionally, we conducted differential expression tests using
1281 Scanpy's 'rank_genes_groups' function with Wilcoxon as the method parameter.
1282

1283

1284 **In-vitro validation experiment: cardiac reprogramming**

1285 Human primary cardiac fibroblasts (HCF, PromoCell, C-12375) of passage number
1286 between 3 – 7 are seeded in 24 well plates of density of 10,000 cells per well, in Growth
1287 medium 3 (PromoCell, C-23025), incubated in 37°C and 5% CO₂ for 1 overnight. On
1288 the next day, HCF assigned for “hMGT” and “Event 2” groups were transfected with
1289 pBabe-miR-133 (Addgene, 172392) by lipofectamine 3000 reagent (Invitrogen,
1290 L3000001) according to manufacturer's instruction. Cells of the “Control” group were
1291 transfected with lipofectamine reagent only. “Event 2” cells are also added with
1292 recombinant human DLL4 protein (R&D Systems, 1506-D4-050/CF, 100 ng/mL). After
1293 48 h of incubation at 37°C and 5% CO₂, the transfection medium was removed, and the
1294 HCF were transduced with lentiviruses carrying *MEF2C*, *GATA4* and *TBX5*, driven by
1295 CMV (for “hMGT” group), or Event 2 vectors (for “Event 2” group) which contains EF1A
1296 promoter-driven *Tet3G*, and TRE3G-driven *HES5*, *SHOX* and *TEAD4*, *ONECUT3* and
1297 *LIN28A*, which are delivered through two lentiviruses. Lentiviruses were transduced in
1298 MOI of 50 per virus. In all groups, HCF is added with Polybrene (Merck, TR-1003-G, 0.4
1299 µL per well) and Cyclosporin H (R&D Systems, 6982/5, 80 µM). In the “Event 2” group,
1300 HCF is also added with recombinant human DLL1 protein (Biolegend, 757404, 100
1301 ng/mL) and Doxycycline Hydrochloride (Merck, D3072-1ML, 1 µg/ml). For the media of
1302 transduction, iCM medium⁵² was used in “hMGT”, and Growth medium 3 was used in
1303 “Event 2” and “control”. After transduction, the plate was centrifuged at 500 g, 32°C for
90 min. After 48 h of 37°C and 5% CO₂ incubation, viruses and other reagents were

1304 removed and exchanged with fresh media, in a 1:1 ratio with B27/Cardio Culture
 1305 Medium (RPMI 1640 with HEPES and GlutaMAX medium supplemented with 2% B27
 1306 with insulin (Gibco))⁶⁴. Cells were further incubated for 5 and 12 days and collected for
 1307 Fluorescence-Activated Cell Sorting (FACS) analysis, qRT-PCR, and
 1308 immunofluorescence staining (IF).

1309

1310 **Lentiviral synthesis**

1311 All the lentiviruses used in this study were synthesized by VectorBuilder. VSV-G
 1312 pseudotyped third-generation lentivirus has been used. All lentiviral experiments have
 1313 obtained the required approval and were performed in the S2 laboratory according to
 1314 the safety guidelines. The gene expression plasmids are as follows:

1315

Gene expression vector	Vector contents
"hMGT" vector (VB230714-1264mjr)	CMV>hMEF2C[NM_001193347.1](ns):P2A:hGATA4[NM_001308093.3](ns):T2A:hTBX5[NM_181486.4]
"Event 2" Tet3G vector (VB010000-4510aas)	pLV[Exp]-Hygro-EF1A>Tet3G
"Event 2" TRE3G-driven HES5, SHOX and TEAD4 vector (VB230223-1163kxh)	TRE3G-driven HES5, SHOX and TEAD4 vector: pLV[Exp]- TRE3G>hHES5[NM_001010926.4](ns):E2A:hSHOX[NM_000451.4](ns):E2A:hTEAD4[NM_003213.4](ns)*:E2A:mKate2
"Event 2" TRE3G-driven ONECUT3 and LIN28A vector (VB230222-1177ywf)	pLV[Exp]- TRE3G>hONECUT3[NM_001080488.2](ns):E2A:hLIN28A[NM_024674.6](ns):E2A:EGFP

1316

1317

1318 **Antibody staining for FACS analysis**

1319 Reprogrammed cells were washed once by PBS and then isolated by incubation in
 1320 trypsin-EDTA (Gibco, 25200072) at 37°C for 5 min, followed by centrifugation in 4°C
 1321 for 5 min in 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes. Supernatants were removed and cells were fixed
 1322 in 4% formaldehyde solution (in PBS) for 5 min, centrifuged in 3,000 g to remove the
 1323 fixative, resuspended with blocking solution (2% BSA in PBS) for 10 min, and re-
 1324 centrifuged. Fixed cell pallets were resuspended with anti-alpha Actinin-Vio® R667
 1325 antibody (Miltenyi Biotec, 130-128-591), or anti-cardiac Troponin T -Vio® R667
 1326 Antibody (Miltenyi Biotec, 130-129-225), which are in 1:400 dilution in blocking
 1327 solution with nuclear labeling dye DAPI (Sigma Aldrich, D8417-10MG). Cells were
 1328 stained for 30 min at room temperature in the dark, followed by centrifugation, PBS
 1329 wash, re-centrifugation, and resuspension in 50 µL PBS for FACS. FACS were performed
 1330 in BD FACSCelesta Cell Analyzer (BD Biosciences). Raw data analysis was performed in
 1331 FlowJo v10 Software (BD Biosciences).

1332

1333 **Cell staining: Immunofluorescence and imaging**

1334 5 – 6 × 10⁴ cells were passaged onto Geltrex-coated 10 mm round coverslips in a 24-
 1335 well format using 0.25 % trypsin/EDTA (Thermo Fisher) and incubated in cardio culture
 1336 medium (RPMI-Glutamax with B27 supplement (Thermo Fisher) supplemented with 20
 1337 % FCS (Thermo Fisher) and 2 µM Thiazovivin (Merck). After 24 h, the medium was
 1338 refreshed to the cardio culture medium. After 4-5 days, the cells were fixated for 20 min
 1339 with 4 % Histofix (Roth), washed in 1x PBS (Thermo Fisher), and stored in blocking
 1340 solution (1 % BSA in 1x PBS) at 4 °C until usage (at least 24 h). In the case of Mitospy

1341 staining, the cells were treated with 250 nM Mitospy-orange (Biolegend) for 30 min at
 1342 37 °C prior to fixation. For IF staining, primary and secondary antibodies were diluted in
 1343 staining solution (0.1 % triton-x in 1 % BSA/PBS). Images were acquired using a SP5
 1344 microscope (Leica). Dilutions and antibodies are summarized as follows:

1345

Primary antibody	Dilution	Secondary antibody	Dilution
Mouse anti- α -actinin Sigma, A7811 RRID: AB_476766	1:300	AF488 donkey anti-rabbit IgG Invitrogen, A31572 RRID AB_162543	1:500
Rabbit anti-Titin MyoMedix, TTN-9 RRID: AB_2734750	1:500	AF647 donkey anti-rabbit Invitrogen, A31573 RRID: AB_2536183	1:500
Mouse anti-Connexin 43 Thermo Fisher, 13-8300 RRID: AB_2533038	1:50	AF488 donkey anti-rabbit IgG Invitrogen, A31572 RRID AB_162543	1:100

1346

1347 For quantification of the mitochondrial network structure, the Mitospy images were
 1348 analyzed using an ImageJ Plugin for Mitochondrial Network Analysis (MiNA)⁵⁴.

1349

1350

1351 **qRT-PCR**

1352 Reprogrammed cells were isolated by the same method as the FACS section. Centrifuged
 1353 cell pellets were resuspended in 100 μ L of extraction buffer from the PicoPure RNA
 1354 Isolation Kit (Applied Biosystems, KIT0214). RNA extractions were performed according
 1355 to the manufacturer's instructions. Genomic DNA removal was performed with an
 1356 RNase-Free DNase Set (Qiagen, 79256). cDNA syntheses were performed with
 1357 RevertAid H Minus First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific, K1632).
 1358 cDNA was diluted in at least 1:3 with nuclease-free water. qRT-PCR was performed with
 1359 iTaq Universal SYBR Green Supermix (BioRad, 1725122), with primers targeting
 1360 *GAPDH*, *COL1A1*, *FN1*, *NKX2-5*, *RYR2*, *KCNJ2*, *CD36* and *MYH6*. The primer
 1361 sequences are as follows:

1362 *GAPDH*:

1363 Forward: 5'-AAAGCCTGCCGGTGAAC-3'

1364 Reverse: 5'-AGGAAAAGCATCACCCGGAG-3'

1365 *COL1A1*:

1366 Forward: 5'-CTGGCAGCCCTGGTGA-3'

1367 Reverse: 5'- CACCATCATTCCACGAGCA-3'

1368 *FN1*:

1369 Forward: 5'-ATGGTTTTAGGCGGACCACA-3'

1370 Reverse: 5'- TCTTGCCTACATTCGGCGG-3'

1371 *CD36*:

1372 Forward: 5'-GCAACAAACCACACTGGG-3'

1373 Reverse: 5'-ACACTGCAGTCCTCAGTACA-3'

1374 *MYH6*:

1375 Forward: 5'-ACCAACCTGTCCAAGTTCCG-3'

1376 Reverse: 5'-TTGCTTGGCACCAATGTAC-3'

1377 *RYR2*:

1378 Forward: 5'-TGAAAGCATCAAACGCAGCA-3'

1379 Reverse: 5'-TCCACCACACAGCCAATCTC-3'

1380 *NKX2-5*:
1381 Forward: 5'-CAACATGACCCTGAGTCCCC-3'
1382 Reverse: 5'-TAATCGCCGCCACAAACTCT-3'
1383 *KCNJ2*:
1384 Forward: 5'-TCCGAGGTCAACAGCTTCAC-3'
1385 Reverse: 5'-TTGGGCATTCATCCGTGACA-3'

1386

1387 **HCR-smFISH protocol**

1388 HCR-smFISH (Molecular Instruments) was performed on the reprogrammed cells
1389 according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, cells are plated onto round glass
1390 coverslips 1 week before HCR-smFISH. On the day of the experiment, cells were washed
1391 by PBS twice, followed by fixation by 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 15 minutes at
1392 room temperature, and then washed again by PBS twice. For hybridization, the cells
1393 were pre-hybridized with 200 μ L of pre-hybridization buffer for 10min at 37°C, which
1394 was then replaced by the Probe Hybridization Solution containing RNA probes that
1395 target *TNNT1*, *KCNJ2*, and *COL1A1*, respectively. Cells were incubated at 37°C for 12
1396 hours, followed by three washes of Probe Wash Buffer for 15min each at 37°C. For
1397 amplification, cells were preincubated with Amplification Buffer for 30min at 37°C,
1398 followed by the addition of Hairpins H1/H2 - Amplification Buffer mix. Amplification
1399 was carried out at room temperature for 12 hours, followed by four washes by Wash
1400 Buffer, 15 minutes each at room temperature. Finally, the antifade mounting reagent was
1401 applied, and the cell coverslips were placed on glass slides for confocal microscopy
1402 imaging.

1403

1404 **Cell collection for single-cell RNA-seq**

1405 Reprogrammed cells from each well were trypsinized using 3mL of Trypsin-EDTA
1406 (0,25%) with phenol red (Gibco, 25200072) for 5min at 37°C, then was transferred to
1407 5mL tube, addition of 2mL of HCF medium and centrifugation (300g, 5min, 4°C). The
1408 pellet from each tube was resuspension by 100 μ L of a unique Cell multiplexing oligo
1409 (1000261, 10x Genomics) for 5min at room temperature, followed by addition of 4mL
1410 of FACS buffer (PBS with 10% FBS containing 1% P/S) and centrifugation (300g, 5min,
1411 4°C). The pellets were resuspended again with 4mL of FACS buffer and centrifugation,
1412 where the process was repeated 3 times in total. Afterwards, cell counting was
1413 performed. Cells from all tubes were pooled together with equal cell numbers, in a total
1414 of up to 16,000 cells to be proceeded to 10x GEM generation.

1415

1416 **Nuclei collection for snRNA-seq**

1417 Cells were trypsinized and pelleted as described above. The pellets were resuspended
1418 by 200 μ L of lysis buffer [Tris-HCl (pH 7.4), 1M; NaCl, 5M; MgCl₂, 1M, IGEPAL CA-630,
1419 0.025% in PBS], incubated on ice for 1min. The mixtures were then mixed with 800 μ L
1420 of wash buffer [1% BSA and 0.2U/ μ L (M0314L, New England Biolabs) Murine RNase
1421 Inhibitor in PBS] and centrifuged (500g, 10min, 4°C). The pellets were resuspended in
1422 1mL of wash buffer, and centrifuged again at 500g for 5min at 4°C. Pellets were
1423 resuspension by 100 μ L of a unique Cell multiplexing oligo (1000261, 10x Genomics)
1424 for 5min at room temperature, followed by addition of 4mL of wash buffer and
1425 centrifugation (500g, 5min, 4°C). The pellets were resuspended again with 4mL of FACS
1426 buffer and centrifugation, where the process was repeated 3 times in total. Afterwards,

1427 nucleus counting was performed. Nuclei from all tubes were pooled together with equal
1428 cell numbers, in a total of up to 16,000 nuclei to be proceeded to 10x GEM generation.
1429

1430 **Sample processing for sequencing**

1431 In each sample, cells or nuclei were loaded into a GEM Chip (10x Genomics, PN-
1432 1000127) and encapsulated into emulsion droplets using the Chromium Controller (10x
1433 Genomics, Pleasanton, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instruction. cDNA
1434 library generation and amplification were performed using the "Chromium Next GEM
1435 Single Cell 3' Reagent Kits v3.1 (Dual Index)" protocol according to the manufacturer's
1436 instructions (10x Genomics, PN-1000268 and PN-1000190). The prepared cDNA
1437 library was then sequenced on the Nextseq2000 platform (Illumina, San Diego, CA,
1438 USA) with paired-end mode, at a sequencing depth of ~20,000 reads per cell/nucleus.
1439 To perform sequence alignment, Cell Ranger v6.1.1. pipeline was used to generate a
1440 digital gene expression matrix starting from raw data. For alignment and quantification
1441 of gene expression, the reference transcriptome has been built using the human Genome
1442 assembly GRCh38 as the reference genome. De-multiplexing of CellPlex barcodes into
1443 individual samples, followed by cell type clustering was performed by Seurat.
1444

1445 **Bulk RNA-sequencing and data analysis**

1446 RNA of the reprogrammed cells was extracted and purified by PicoPure™ RNA Isolation
1447 Kit (KIT0204, Applied Biosystems) according to the manufacturer's instruction, with
1448 DNase treatment performed by RNase-Free DNase Set (79254, Qiagen). Purified RNA
1449 was stored at -80°C until library preparation. Library preparation was performed by
1450 TruSeq mRNA Stranded Library Prep Kit (1/2 volume) according to the manufacturer's
1451 instruction (Illumina). To perform bulk RNA sequencing, 400M (covering 18 samples);
1452 1x100 single-ended sequencing was performed in the Nextseq2000 platform. After
1453 sequencing, the FASTQ files were aligned by Kallisto "kallisto quant" function, using
1454 Homo sapiens GRCh38.99 as the reference genome.

1455 RNA sequencing data processing and differential expression analysis were performed
1456 using R (v4.1.0) with the tximport, DESeq2, ggplot2, pheatmap, biomaRt, and vsn
1457 packages. Raw transcript abundance estimates were obtained from Kallisto output files
1458 across 18 samples. Transcript IDs were mapped to gene symbols using Ensembl's
1459 biomaRt, and gene-level expression matrices were generated using tximport. A DESeq2
1460 dataset was created with the design formula ~ condition, and low-count genes were
1461 filtered (row sums ≥ 10). Differential expression analysis was conducted by applying
1462 thresholds of $p_{adj} < 0.01$ and $|\log_2FC| \geq 1.5$. Variance stabilization transformation (VST)
1463 was applied, followed by principal component analysis (PCA) and hierarchical clustering
1464 to visualize sample relationships. Heatmaps of the top differentially expressed genes and
1465 preselected cardiac markers were generated using pheatmap, with the scaled gene
1466 expression matrix.

1467

1468

1469

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1471

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1612

1613 **Data availability:**

1614 All the datasets analyzed in this manuscript are publicly available under accession codes
1615 in the referenced studies. The bulk RNA-seq and scRNA-seq data generated for the
1616 cardiac reprogramming experiments have been deposited at GEO under accession
1617 number GSE289978.

1618

1619 **Code availability:**

1620 The Cell-DRL software and tutorial are available at [https://gitlab.com/ama.bioinfo/cell-](https://gitlab.com/ama.bioinfo/cell-drl)
1621 [drl](https://gitlab.com/ama.bioinfo/cell-drl). Additionally, the Cell-DRL documentation can be found here: [https://cell-](https://cell-drl.gitbook.io/cell-drl-agent/)
1622 [drl.gitbook.io/cell-drl-agent/](https://cell-drl.gitbook.io/cell-drl-agent/)

1623

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1634 Maximilians-Universität Würzburg filed a patent for the Cell-DRL architecture and its
1635 applications for disease trajectory reconstruction under the patent applications number
1636 EP24165826.9 and PCT/EP2025/057639.

1637

1638 **Author contributions:**

1639 AM conceived the concept of Cell-DRL. AM and DG conceived the algorithm and
1640 designed the study. AM developed the algorithm and the analytical framework,
1641 implemented the Cell-DRL software, and conducted all computational analyses. AM and
1642 AC designed the in vitro validation experiment with input from KSB and DG. AC
1643 conducted the in-vitro validation experiments. AC and SR performed the
1644 immunofluorescence and imaging experiments under the supervision of KSB. DG
1645 supervised the project. AM, AC, and DG wrote the manuscript. All authors read and
1646 approved the final manuscript.

1647

1648 **Competing interests:**

1649 DG serves on the scientific advisory board of Gordian Biotechnology.

1650